

East Meets West

Collocation and colligation analysis of "vaccine"
with the keywords: Pfizer, Moderna, Sinovac, and Novavax

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1. Introduction

COVID-19 has been one of the most devastating diseases the world has ever seen. The pandemic caused great losses in all countries, and at the same time, human nations innovated vaccines to fight back. Amidst a political schism and a changing world order, major countries in the east and the west have researched and launched vaccines for their citizens and allies'. As a linguist, it is interesting to find out the sense of political power associated with the language usage during this critical moment. This corpus-based study examines the word "vaccine" in a self-made corpus with the keywords of four leading vaccine brands from the east and the west: Pfizer, Moderna, Sinovac, and Novavax. The word "vaccine" is analyzed in terms of its collocation and colligation. The study also categorizes semantic preference and semantic prosody of the word "vaccine" considering a different level of 1 and 2 words that follow it, in other words, at N+1 and N+2 positions in the KWIC (Keyword in Context) display.

1.1. What is the question?

With the keywords of major vaccine brands from the east and the west in the self-made corpus, the study aims to answer the following research questions:

- I. What are the collocates of "vaccine" in the corpus?
- II. How do language users prefer to use "vaccine" in a context?
- III. How do language users perceive "vaccine"?

1.2. Motivation of the question

Apart from the current heated political atmosphere, the study is inspired by the article The search for units of meaning (Sinclair. 2004[1996]). The article presents a collocation and colligation analysis that can be applied in the context of "vaccine" to answer the research questions.

1.3. Overview of previous work

Xia, Ganlin, Chen, Yiting & Lu Lijing (2022) examined the vaccine's collocates in the Coronavirus corpus using Discourse Analysis method and found that people are concerned about global progress, equality, and the latest development of vaccines. The finding in this article is in

accordance with what is examined here about the reliability, progress, and development of the vaccines.

Baroiant Teni (2015) used the same method, corpus linguistics combined with critical discourse analysis, to analyze online news media. This study revealed that online media constructs a positive bias towards people who vaccinate (contributing to herd immunity) and a negative one for those who do not (detracting from herd immunity). Furthermore, the results confirm that: (1) a threat to public health is perceived towards those who are unvaccinated; and (2) the media generate doubt in regard to vaccine safety. Although this study used various forms of analysis from concordance to collocation, it did not seem to be statistically based.

Despite the recency of the COVID-19 vaccine existence, there have been numerous studies of the sentiment towards the vaccines in online social media, especially on Twitter and reddit. For instance, Navin Kumar and his team (2022) studied COVID-19 vaccine perceptions in the initial phases of US vaccine roll-out on reddit using Social Network Analysis (SNA). The result shows that there was an attempt to improve the perception of vaccine reliability and reduce misinformation especially during the early phases of vaccine roll-out.

In Sinclair's article (2004), the search for units of meaning, a semantic boundary of several phrases was examined using collocation and colligation analysis. The analysis showed that the phrase "the naked eye" has different semantic preferences at a different position. For example, at N-3 position, there is a semantic preference of visibility, and at N-4 position it expresses the prosody of difficulty. One limitation in Sinclair's article could be the fact that the sample is selected randomly from the corpus. Each search in the corpus will not yield the same result.

A more relevant work may be the one of Wulansari's (2021). She studied the word "vaccine" in terms of semantic preference and semantic prosody using a sub-corpus in the Covid-19 corpus in Sketch Engine. The study did not conclude or categorize semantic preference and semantic prosody in the form of a broad theme but, instead, analyzing based on the dictionary meanings of the vocabularies found as collocates.

This study, therefore, shares the elements of those previous work in terms of research methodology, tools, and datasets. In addition, this study employs the powerful visualization tool,

Tableau, to conduct a statistically based analysis and also offers a thorough guideline on the analysis processes to be in accordance with reproducibility and open-data principles. The dataset, the corpus, is also provided as a separate file on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7465522>.

1.4. Formulation of hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following hypotheses has been formulated:

- I. If the keywords of the leading vaccine brands from the east and the west are used to create a corpus, there would be the collocates which show a political sense co-occurring with the word “vaccine”.
- II. Language users would prefer to use and perceive “vaccine” as a tool to fight COVID-19.

2. Methods

2.1. Defining variables

To be aligned with and clearly understand the analysis of the study, there are the terms below which should be given a definition or a scope of meaning.

The term collocation was coined by John Rupert Firth in the 1950s to mean the common co-occurrence of particular words. The British linguist famously said “You shall know a word by the company it keeps” (Firth. 1957). Collocation analysis is, therefore, the analysis of the co-occurring words. He also gave a definition of colligation as the co-occurrence of grammatical choices.

Semantic preference can be defined as the relation between a word form and set of semantically related words (Begagić. 2013).

Lastly, semantic prosody is the spreading of connotational coloring beyond single word boundaries (Partington. 1998: 68). Sinclair (1999) also mentioned that “When the usage of a word gives an impression of an attitudinal or pragmatic meaning, this is called a semantic prosody.”

2.2. Choice of methods

To examine the collocates, semantic preference, and semantic prosody, the study uses collocation and colligation analysis. In the collocation analysis, the regular expression formula [vaccine].[n*] is used to match “vaccine” as a noun in the corpus. The window span is 3L to 3R which means the adjacent 3 words before and after “vaccine” are chosen in the search. Since the word “vaccine” is a noun, it can take a verb in the front and a possible modifier after. A minimum frequency is set at 3.

For the colligation analysis, KWIC (Keyword in Context) display is used with the word “vaccine”. Context size is set at 10 tokens. In the N+1 level, the sort option is as follows: Sort 1 = 1R, Sort 2 = C, Sort 3 = C and order by frequency. For the N+2 level, change Sort 2 to 2R.

2.3. Source of data

The main dataset is this study gathered from Sketch Engine. Sketch Engine is a corpus manager and text analysis software (“Sketch Engine.” 2022). With the feature to build a new corpus, the keywords: Pfizer, Moderna, Sinovac, and Novavax are specified. The website returns a corpus with the size of 947,651 tokens and allows for downloading in a .txt format for further analysis in Antconc programme, for example.

Antconc programme enables a more thorough analysis of KWIC because a full table of results can be downloaded compared with only a number of randomly selected concordances in COHA (Corpus of Contemporary American English).

2.4. Software that was used

The main programme used in the collocation analysis is Antconc version 3.5.9 window (2020). For the colligation analysis, Antconc version 4.1.4 (October, 2022) on Mac is used. Antconc enables the users to save the search result as a text file or datatable. In this case, the search result is saved in datatable because it will be processed in Microsoft Excel. The files for N+1 and N+2 levels are then filtered using Microsoft Excel and loaded to Tableau Public to analyze the frequency percentage.

2.5. Data filtering/annotation

The N+1 and N+2 files are opened in Microsoft Excel to remove irrelevant columns. The only columns which are kept are kwic_id and R0 - R3 for N+1 level and kwic_id and R0 - R5 for N+2 level.

kwic_id	R0	R1	R2	R3
20	vaccine	is	produced	by
29	vaccine	is	likely	to
86	vaccine	is	used	in
92	vaccine	is	officially	called
97	vaccine	is	most	effective
119	vaccine	is	in	use
120	vaccine	is	in	use
150	vaccine	is	only	the
177	vaccine	is	approved	by
179	vaccine	is	the	protein
199	vaccine	is	not	a
214	vaccine	is	just	one
218	vaccine	is	the	ease
232	vaccine	is	and	why

(Screenshot 1: Corpus Dataset)

3. Results

3.1. Collocation Analysis

Rank	Freq	Freq(L)	Freq(R)	Stat	Collocate
1	10	2	8	6.29393	nationalism
2	5	1	4	6.14192	viability
3	4	4	0	6.14192	validates
4	3	3	0	6.14192	trefis
5	3	2	1	6.14192	shingrix
6	3	3	0	6.14192	rushes
7	3	3	0	6.14192	ptau
8	5	0	5	6.14192	psv
9	3	3	0	6.14192	parainfluenza
10	3	0	3	6.14192	morena
11	5	1	4	6.14192	lobby
12	3	3	0	6.14192	licensee

(Screenshot 2: Collocation Analysis on Antconc Windows)

Based on the collocation search, the most frequent collocate of “vaccine” is “nationalism” with the frequency of 10 followed by “viability” (5) and “validates” (4). The third collocate “validate” occurs specifically with Sinovac vaccine as in “WHO validates Sinovac COVID-19 vaccine.”

3.2. Colligation Analysis

The colligation analysis is executed using Antconc version 4.1.4 on Macbook with the searching term “vaccine”. After opening the .txt corpus file that is saved from Sketch Engine, on the “KWIC” tab, type “vaccine” in the search box. Context size is 10 tokens. For N+1, make sure that Sort 1 is set at 1R, Sort 2 and Sort 3 is set to C. For N+2, Sort 1 is set at 1R, Sort 2 at 2R, and Sort 3 to C. There will be the same number of hit results for both N+1 and N+2 at 14,970 hits, but the N+2 result will be arranged by the frequency of the second word after “vaccine” instead of the first word for N+1. Therefore, the analysis for both levels will be different. The last step in the Antconc programme is to save the file by clicking “File” > “Save Current Tab DataTables”. Name it KWIC N+1 and KWIC N+2 accordingly.

(Screenshot 3: KWIC Display in Antconc on Mac)

3.2.1. N+1 Level

Since the analysis scope at N+1 level is not large, some data filtering can be done using Microsoft Excel. After opening the KWIC N+1 in Excel, delete all the columns except kwic_id, R0, R1, R2, and R3. Export the file as .csv to be used in Tableau. The first thing is to find some semantic characteristics from the big picture.

(Screenshot 4: An Overview of Colligation Analysis of N+1 Position in Tableau)

https://public.tableau.com/views/ENG-Ling350CorpusLinguistics-KWICN1/KWICN1Overview?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link

3.2.1.1. An Overview

- 3.2.1.1.1. First, the text file N+1 and N+2 is uploaded to Tableau one at a time.
- 3.2.1.1.2. Then, a new sheet is opened.
- 3.2.1.1.3. On the “Tables” module on the left hand side, double click to select R0, R1, and R2. Bring all three to the “Columns” section.
- 3.2.1.1.4. Click and drag R1 to “Rows” and select “Measure (Count)” in order to calculate the frequency of N+1 word in percent.

- 3.2.1.1.5. Click “R1” in “Rows” again and go to “Quick Table Calculation”. Select “Percent of Total”.
- 3.2.1.1.6. Click “R1” in “Rows”, select “Compute Using”, and tick “Table (across)”.

- 3.2.1.1.7. To filter out the low frequency collocates and to see the high frequency ones more clearly, click “R1” in “Rows” and select “Show Filter”. On the top right of the chart, move the minimum percentage up to 0.167%.
- 3.2.1.1.8. To highlight the findings, select the bar charts “will be”, “may be”, “can be”, and “could be” altogether by holding a command key. Right click and select “Create Set”. Name the set “highlight”.
- 3.2.1.1.9. Drag the “highlight” under the “Tables” module to “Color” under the “Marks” module.
- 3.2.1.1.10. Adjust the color by double clicking the color icon on the top right of the chart.

Based on the chart, at N+1 level, the prominent characteristic is the presence of modal verbs “can”, “could”, “may”, as well as an auxiliary verb “will”.

At this point, I was suspecting that there must be other verbs apart from “be” that follow “can”, “could”, “may”, and “will”, so I took a closer look at these verbs in a new sheet.

3.2.1.2. A Closer Look

(Screenshot 5: A Closer Look of Colligation Analysis of N+1 Position in Tableau)

https://public.tableau.com/views/ENG-Ling350CorpusLinguistics-KWIC/KWICN1CloserLook?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link

- 3.2.1.2.1. On a new sheet, put “R0”, “R1”, and “R2” in “Rows”.
- 3.2.1.2.2. Put “R1” in “Columns” and calculate it by selecting “Measure (Count)”, “Quick Table Calculation” > “Percent of Total”, and “Compute Using” > “Table (down)”.

3.2.1.2.3. Filter “R1” in “Rows” and search for “can”, “could”, “may”, and “will” in the filter pane on the top right of the chart.

3.2.1.2.4. For each search, tick relevant verb forms. For example, when searching for the verb “will”, only “will”, “Will”, and “will-” are selected.

3.2.1.2.5. The filtered result will show on the chart. We can see that there are many other verbs that follow “will”, so the percentage of frequency at N+1 for “will” should include these verbs too. Select all the bars, right click on the bars, and select “group”. Name the group “will”

3.2.1.2.6. Repeat the same filtering steps for all the remaining verbs. Do not forget to remove the previous search filter before selecting a new verb.

3.2.1.2.7. The group “R1 (group)” will appear in the “Tables” module on the left panel.

3.2.1.3. The Real Number

(Screenshot 6: The Main Words of Colligation Analysis of N+1 Position in Tableau)

(https://public.tableau.com/views/ENG-Ling350CorpusLinguistics-KWIC/KWICN1TheRealNumber?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

- 3.2.1.3.1. On a new sheet, put “R1 (group)” to “Columns” and “R1” in “Rows”.
- 3.2.1.3.2. Calculate “R1” by selecting “Measure (Count)”, “Quick Table Calculation” > “Percent of Total”, and “Compute Using” > “Table (across)”.
- 3.2.1.3.3. Put “R1 (group)” in the “Color” icon under the “Marks” module.

Here, we can make a more inclusive analysis of the dominant character at N+1 level. The previous overview analysis shows that the dominant character at the N+1 level is the use of modal verbs “can”, “could”, and “may”, as well as an auxiliary verb “will”.

With this graph, we can see that the three modal verbs account for 1.78% comprising “can” at 0.62%, “may” at 0.61%, and “could” at 0.55%. The verb “will” occurs 1.04%. More extended details can be found by right clicking the bar and selecting “View Data”. Select the tab “Full Data”.

R1 (group)	Kwic Id	R0	R1	R2	R3
will, Will, will-	7189	vaccine	will	be	priced
will, Will, will-	2069	vaccine	will	be	ready
will, Will, will-	5556	vaccine	will	be	ready
will, Will, will-	11665	vaccine	will	be	referred
will, Will, will-	4332	vaccine	will	be	required
will, Will, will-	1025	vaccine	will	be	rolled
will, Will, will-	7319	vaccine	will	be	shipped
will, Will, will-	4296	vaccine	will	be	significantly
will, Will, will-	719	vaccine	will	be	similar
will, Will, will-	160	vaccine	will	be	stored
will, Will, will-	4754	vaccine	will	be	the
will, Will, will-	4720	vaccine	will	be	there
will, Will, will-	850	vaccine	will	be	uploaded
will, Will, will-	4205	vaccine	will	be	widely
will, Will, will-	12052	vaccine	will	be	widely

R1 (group)	Kwic Id	R0	R1	R2	R3
will, Will, will-	714	vaccine	will	result	in
will, Will, will-	11789	vaccine	will	start "	immediately"
will, Will, will-	507	vaccine	will	stay	ahead
will, Will, will-	8429	vaccine	will	still	be
will, Will, will-	12829	vaccine	will	still	be
will, Will, will-	2761	vaccine	will	stimulate	your
will, Will, will-	2040	vaccine	will	take	delivery
will, Will, will-	715	vaccine	will	take	place
will, Will, will-	12837	vaccine	will	take	place
will, Will, will-	1269	vaccine	will	trigger	the
will, Will, will-	445	vaccine	will	work	against
will, Will, will-	13176	vaccine	will	work	doc
will, Will, will-	13197	vaccine	will	work	doc
will, Will, will-	6664	vaccine	will-	receive-	fda-
will, Will, will-	6665	vaccine	will-	receive-	fda-

(Screenshot 7 and 8: The Full Data of “Will” in Colligation Analysis of N+1 Position in Tableau)

The full data reveals a particularly interesting phenomena because it shows that these verbs have 2 functions: the main function is the passive voice construction “be+past participle”, and another function is a descriptive one. For example, “will” is used in the passive voice construction as in “will be + past participle”: vaccine will be priced, vaccine will be stored, and vaccine will be uploaded. “Will” is also followed by an infinitive verb to indicate an actual action or a consequence related to vaccine, such as vaccine will start, vaccine will stimulate, and vaccine will trigger.

3.2.2. N+2 Level

For N+2 level, since the analysis frame will expand more, the KWIC N+2 downloaded from Antconc can be uploaded straight to Tableau. Tableau will name the R0 column R01, R1 R11, and R2 R21 respectively. Now, we can try to look for semantic preference and semantic prosody by looking at the big picture at N+2 level.

(Screenshot 9: Colligation Analysis of N+2 Position in Tableau)

(https://public.tableau.com/views/KWICN2/KWICN2?:language=en-US&publish=yes&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

3.2.2.1. An Overview

- 3.2.2.1.1. On a new sheet, bring “R01 R11 R21 and R3” to “Rows” and R3 to “Columns”.
- 3.2.2.1.2. On R3 in “Columns”, select “Measure (Count)”, “Quick Table Calculation” > “Percent of Total”, and “Compute Using” > “Table (down)”.
- 3.2.2.1.3. Click on “Label” under the “Marks” module and tick “Show Mark Labels” to display the percentage numbers.
- 3.2.2.1.4. To filter out small percentage words, click “CNT(R3)” and “Show Filter”. The filter window will appear on the top right of the chart.
- 3.2.2.1.5. Adjust the filter to 0.0380%.
- 3.2.2.1.6. Right click all the bar charts with the passive voice constructions while holding a command key.
- 3.2.2.1.7. Right click again and select “Group”. Select “R21” level.

3.2.2.1.8. Adjust the color of the passive voice bars by double clicking the “R1(Group)” window on the right panel.

Based on the observation, various forms of passive voice construction are found. The most predominant one is “is+past participle” at 0.3243% followed by “was+past participle” at 0.2703% and “has (not)+been+past participle” at 0.1622%. Some passive voice construction with modal verbs are also detected; for example, “can be+past participle” at 0.0946%, “may be+past participle” at 0.0473%, and “must be+past participle” at 0.0405%.

The words associated with the passive voice constructions are administered, approved, produced, authorized, developed, distributed, and made. They signify different stages of vaccine from development and approval to production and distribution.

In addition, vaccine is described for its reliability with the adjective “safe” at 0.1149%, as well as the phrase “has an efficacy of...%” at 0.0473% and “vaccine effectiveness against severe (and mild) disease” at 0.0405%.

4. Summary and Discussion

Based on the result, the word “vaccine”, examined in the corpus built with the searching keywords of the leading vaccine brands from the east and the west, demonstrates a sense of nationalism in the collocation analysis. In the colligation analysis at N+1 level, it has been found that language users prefer to use modal verbs “can”, “could”, and “may” which signal uncertainty and probability, as well as an auxiliary verb “will” which indicates future actions and consequences. Therefore, semantic preference at N+1 level is related to uncertainty, probability, and future actions and consequences. At N+2 level, a high number of passive voice constructions have been detected using verb to be or with a modal verb. A strong semantic preference of vaccine’s reliability and its stages from development to distribution is found. With the use of modal verbs and passive voice constructions, the word “vaccine” in the corpus portrays a prominent semantic prosodic of an object. In everyday use of language, it is more common to find the use of modal verbs “can”, “could”, and “may” with an object or abstraction as in “It can be...” or “It may be...” than “She or he can be...”. “Vaccine”, in this case, is strongly perceived as an object.

To sum up, the first hypothesis is confirmed in that a sense of politics is shown up as the first collocate; however, the second hypothesis is not fully fulfilled because people do not perceive “vaccine” as a tool to fight COVID-19 virus but an object that is described in terms of the progress and reliability, as well as an object of actions.

For future work, it would be interesting to examine a semantic preference and semantic prosody at other levels, such as N-1 and N-2. Also, the difference of semantic preference between main characteristics should be further studied. With reference to this study, it could be the difference of semantic preference found between each modal verb. Moreover, an extensive analysis on the modal verbs in terms of epistemic, deontic, and dynamic modality could be conducted.

5. References

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